

PIKUL - HISTORY AND REALITY

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Abstract: Pikul's works have always aroused the interest of readers and historians. In this article we have analyzed some of Pikul's works in terms of history, as well as personal attitude, volumetric images of the characters, their emotions and experiences, everyday life of the era, which the author sought to show and showed.

Keywords: history, everyday life, press, prototype, interest, authenticity.

In the mid-eighties of the last century, readers, in addition to relevant articles in the press, showed great interest in the past of their country. The familiar textbook portraits of historical figures were no longer satisfying - we wanted something new, out-of-the-box.

It was this unconventional approach to Russian history that gave readers Valentin Pikul, a writer whose book circulation during this period was breaking all records. The main interest of his life was literature. He devoted a lot of time to self-education, went to the literary circle, communicated with young writers.

Note that Pikul's first published story had nothing to do with history at all - it was an informative article about ginseng. Pikul was contemplating the idea of his first novel when he came across a book about the Northern Fleet destroyers. Pikul found it very boring and decided that he could write much better on this subject close to him. But several versions of the conceived story were destroyed by him, because Pikul considered them unsuccessful. Nevertheless, some of these materials were published as fragments in the Tallinn naval newspaper "On Watch".

Pikul's literary success came after the release of his first novel, Ocean Patrol, devoted to the struggle against the Nazis in the Barents Sea. The sea theme was one of the main ones in his work, but it was not the only one. His works covered several centuries of Russian history, from the time of the Russian Empire to the Great Patriotic War.

Pikul was an extremely prolific author by the standards of the time, when most writers were in the habit of creating books on their own. For 40 years of his creative life he created about 30 novels and novellas, not counting numerous historical miniatures - small stories about historical personalities and events of the past.

In the early 1960s Pikul moved to Riga, where he lived until his death. It was there that he created his most famous works, such as Requiem for the PQ-17 Caravan, Moonsund, Word and Deed and others.

Pikul's style was quite different from the classic historical novels of the Soviet era. In his books the author put a personal touch, drew very volumetric images of the characters, showing their emotions and experiences, colorfully described the life of that era. At the same time the main characters of Pikulia often became not fictional characters or prototypes of famous figures, but the most real historical figures.

Pikul in his works is not a detached conventional author, but an emotional storyteller who openly sympathizes with some personalities and is completely ruthless to others.

This method of narration did not please the writer's colleagues, alarmed professional historians and attracted the close attention of the authorities of the time, who saw in Pikul's irreverence for Empress Elizaveta Petrovna, Catherine the Great and Grigory Potemkin some hidden hints of modernity.

This is why Pikul's real success came during perestroika, when it became fashionable to allow everything and everyone.

The more popular the writer's books became, the more harshly he was criticized by professional historians. Fans of Pikul to this day take such criticism with a rod, arguing that the author before each book worked a lot with the sources. Opponents object - Pikul did not spend a day in the archives, preferring to work with memoirs of participants of events or with the books of those writers who have already created works on this topic.

Connoisseurs of the history of the fleet notice that Pikul, despite his own naval past, sometimes very freely describes naval battles, gives incorrect characteristics of the ships, and even the portraits of some naval commanders and does not look caricatured.

Pikul's factual inaccuracies are indeed very numerous, but, mainly, the complaints are not about them, but about the historical portraits of the personalities he described. In his unfinished novel "Barbarossa" Valentin Pikul gave an extremely derogatory characterization of the entire Soviet leadership during the Great Patriotic War, almost without hesitation in expressions.

Professional historians note - in his story the writer often intertwined events that never really happened and appear only as rumors and historical anecdotes. Pikul, on the other hand, presented it as an immutable truth.

But if the unfinished Barbarossa, which came out at the height of the revelations of the Soviet system, Pikul was forgiven, then for the novel Unclean Power many admirers of The Russia We Lost even today are ready to anathematize the author posthumously.

Both admirers and critics of Valentin Pikul make the same mistake trying to evaluate him as a historian. Pikul is not a historian, he is a creator of historical novels.

He was once called the "Russian Dumas," and this is a very accurate characterization. After all, the France created by Alexandre Dumas was radically different from the real France. For someone who grew up with The Three Musketeers, it is difficult to accept the idea that Richelieu, Anne of Austria, Buckingham in reality were quite different from the way Dumas described them. But the writer's genius was stronger than the historical truth.

Almost the same situation with the works of Pikul. His historical narrative - the author's view of the era, not claiming absolute objectivity. The magic of Pikul's works led many to believe that everything he told - the truth from beginning to end. When it turned out that this is not the case, disappointment set in.

The real merit of Valentin Pikulia is that he was able to awaken a genuine interest in history in millions of readers. Many modern professional historians admit that their choice of life path was influenced by Pikul's books read in their youth. And the fact that much in his novels is not confirmed by historical documents, so the history as a science and differs from fiction.

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